

STANDARDIZATION OF *KOSHATAKYADI YAVAGU* AN AYURVEDIC AGADA FORMULATIONDr. Athulya C. M.*¹, Dr. Abhay H. Patkar²¹Ph.D. Scholar, Dept. of Agadtantra, ASS Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nashik, India.²H.O.D. & Professor, Dept. of Agadtantra, ASS Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Nashik, India.

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ABSTRACT

Koshatakyadi agada is mentioned in the *Sushrut Samhita Kalpasthana* 2nd chapter *Sthaavaravishavijnaniya adyaya* in the form of *Yavagu* which can be given in both *Sthavara* and *Jangama visha*. This *Yoga* consists of 20 herbal drugs and *Rakta shali* is used for preparing *Yavagu*. In this study the standardization of *Koshatakyadi yavagu* is done by evaluating its physicochemical, phytochemical, photo spectrometric and nutritional value.

KEYWORDS: *Koshatakyadi agada, Yavagu, Standardization, Pathya Kalpana.*

INTRODUCTION

Pathya Kalpana represents a very critical foundation and major aspect of Ayurvedic theory, and it refers to the cooking or preparation of food items using the *Samskara* or methods of processing the food for the purpose of increasing the therapeutic capacity of the food and the health benefits associated with it. One such preparation, known as *Yavagu* which is commonly consumed as gruel or porridge made mainly with rice represents one of the most important and primary forms of *Pathya Kalpana*. *Yavagu* is also high in carbohydrates, easily digestible, and contains a very high nutritional value, therefore making it an ideal method of food consumption for both healthy individuals and ill individuals; however, *Yavagu* is especially recommended for people suffering from *Mandagni*.

Ayurvedic literature identifies three principal types of *Yavagu* as mentioned in **Figure 1**; *Kalka Siddha Yavagu*, *Mamsa Rasa Siddha Yavagu* and *Kwatha Siddha Yavagu*. *Kalka Siddha Yavagu* made by combining a paste with the base gruel; *Kwatha Siddha Yavagu* made by combining a decoction of medicinal drugs with the base gruel; and *Mamsa Rasa Siddha*

Yavagu made by using meat broth to produce the base of the gruel.

Figure 1: Various principal types of *Yavagu*.

The *Charaka Samhita* provides an extensive description of twenty-eight varieties of *Yavagu*, which have been altered according to the specific requirements of a particular disease that would be treated with a specific formulation of the decocted drugs added to the *Yavagu* Type food preparation. *Koshatakyadi Yavagu*, or *Yavagu* of the *Koshatakya* family, is mentioned in classical literature in association with *Visha Chikitsa* and is

specifically recommended for a variety of conditions including the genus of *Visha Vegantara*.

Contents of *Koshatakyadi yavagu*

1. *Koshataki (Luffa Acutangula)*
2. *Agnika (Apium Graveolens)*
3. *Pata (Cyclea Peltate)*
4. *Amruta (Tinospora Cordifolia)*
5. *Haritaki (Terminalia Chebula)*
6. *Shirisha (Albizia Lebbeck)*
7. *Kinihi (Apāmarga) (Achyranthes Aspera)*
8. *Shelu (Cordia Dichotoma)*
9. *Haridra (Curcuma Longa)*
10. *Daruharidra (Berberis Aristata)*
11. *Shweta Punarnava (Boerhavia Diffusa)*
12. *Rakta Punarnava (Trianthema Portulacastrum)*
13. *Shunti (Zingiber Officinale)*
14. *Maricha (Piper Nigrum)*
15. *Pippali (Piper Longum)*
16. *Sariva (Hemidesmus Indicus)*
17. *Bala (Sida Cordifolia)*
18. *Suryavalli (Holostemma Adakodein)*
19. *Giryahva (Clitorea Ternatea)*
20. *Harenu (Nirgundi Beeja)*
21. *Rakta Shali (Oryza Sativa)*

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Koshatakyadi yavagu choorna, *Kashaya* and *Yavagu* are prepared according to the textual reference. Analytical test of the *Choorna*, *Kashaya* and *Yavagu* was done in the *Bhide* foundation research laboratory, Pune according to the CCRAS guidelines for checking its physicochemical, phytochemical and photospectrometric properties.

TLC Method of *Koshatakyadi choorna*

TLC was carried out on thin-layer chromatography pre-coated silica gel 60F-254, solvent system containing Toluene: Ethyl Acetate (8:2 v/v), Test Solution

containing 1 gm sample added about 5 ml of methanol heated on water bath for 5 minutes and filtered out for further process.

PROCEDURE

For each solution tested, 10 micro-liters were placed onto a TLC plate as 10 mm bands. The plate was developed until the solvent front was 8 cm from the line of application; the plate was then air dried and heated to 110°C for approximately 5 minutes or until the bands were clearly visible. After that, the bands were observed, and R_f values were calculated.

RESULTS

Prepared *Yavagu* was tested in FHHL Private Limited, Pune for checking its nutritive value; results are mentioned in **Tables 1-4**. Based on the compiled laboratory data and analysis, the prepared samples were assessed for overall quality. Results showed that they had good physical and chemical characteristics. Powdered form exhibited good organoleptic properties; no evidence of foreign materials; an overall uniform particle size; a good level of ash & extractive properties suggesting a high degree of purity and well-prepared product. The *Kashaya* formulations also indicated an acceptable specific gravity profile, a mild acidic pH, as well as standard extractive parameters showing there is a high level of stability/consistency in formulation preparation.

Studies of *Yavagu* preparations showed that they had superior sensory characteristics and evaluated them for the presence of phyto-constituents, specifically alkaloids, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, and saponins; demonstrating the potential for therapeutic uses. Physicochemical properties also supported quality with both low moisture content and balanced levels of extractable.

Table 1: Description of *Choorna*.

S. No.	Tests	Results
1.	Description	Light brown colour powder
2.	Odour	Characteristic
3.	Colour	Brown
4.	Taste	Bitter
5.	Foreign Matter	Nil
6.	Particle size	100% pass through 80 mesh
7.	Loss on drying	6.24 %
8.	Total ash	6.95 %
9.	Acid insoluble ash	4.19 %
10.	Alcohol soluble extract	70.62 %
11.	Water soluble extract	87.50%
12.	pH	5.50

Table 2: Quality Description of *Kashaya*.

S. No.	Tests	Results
1.	Specific gravity	1.018 g/ml
2.	Ph	4.71
3.	Refractive Index	4.800
4.	Water soluble extract	2.48 %

Table 3: Quality Description of *Yavagu*.

S. No.	Tests	Results
1.	Appearance	Soft & smooth
2.	Odour	Aromatic
3.	Colour	Brown
4.	Touch	Smooth
5.	Alkaloids	Present
6.	Tannins	Absent
7.	Phenolic Compound	Present
8.	Flavonoids	Present
9.	Glycosides	Absent
10.	Saponins	Present
11.	Loss on drying	2.28%
12.	Total ash	7.19 %
13.	Water soluble extract	33.18%
14.	Alcohol soluble extract	64.38 %
15.	pH	5.50

Table 4: Nutritional Value of *Koshatakyadi Yavagu*.

S. No.	Test Done	Result	Unit	Test Method
1.	Protein	4.42	g/100g	IS 7219 (Modified method by FOSS Kjeltex): 1973
2.	Fat	4.70	g/100g	IS 6287 Cl. No. 10: 1985
3.	Carbohydrate (Available)	27.81	g/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/17(f) Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
4.	Energy	171.22	Kcal/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/17(f) Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
5.	Saturated Fat	3.19	g/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/31 Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
6.	Monounsaturated Fat	1.16	g/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/31 Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
7.	Polyunsaturated Fat	0.32	g/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/31 Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
8.	Trans Fat	0.11	g/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/31 Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
9.	Sodium	16.86	mg/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/74 Issue No.2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
10.	Total Sugar	10.19	g/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/78 Issue No. 02 Issue Date 01 June 2022
11.	Cholesterol	0.83	mg/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/30 Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022
12.	Added sugar	<0.5	g/100g	FHHL/SOP/CHEM/F/78 Issue No. 2 Issue Date 01 June 2022

Nutritional evaluation of *Koshatakyadi Yavagu* indicated that the product contained moderate quantities of energy; considerable amounts of carbohydrates, protein, and fats; low sodium, low added sugars; and negligible cholesterol, making it also very beneficial nutritionally and therefore usable both as a food and therapeutic preparation.

DISCUSSION

Standardization of formulation helps in defining its quality, efficacy and authentication. Through the various

standardization procedure of Ayurvedic formulations are opening a pathway for better identification of this science to the outside world. *Koshatakyadi agada* even though mentioned as an *Agada*, by understanding its analytical properties and nutritive value it provides a wide range of its use as a medicine as well as a food supplement in various disease conditions.

CONCLUSION

After conducting both nutritional analysis and analytical evaluations there were similar results confirming that

Koshatakyadi Yavagu has desirable physicochemical and organoleptic qualities. Varying phyto-constituents in the formulation demonstrate its potential as a therapeutic agent, along with providing a balanced nutritional composition. Therefore, *Koshatakyadi Yavagu* is a standardized, safe and effective formulation to be used in both a medicinal and nutritional manner.

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